

Effect of Forensic Accounting Practices on Fraud Detection: A Study of Economic and Financial Crimes Commission in Nigeria

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Received: 20.05.2025 | Accepted: 29.05.2024 | Published: 31.05.2025

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DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15564789](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15564789)

Abstract

Case Studies

The increasing incidence of financial crimes in Nigeria has necessitated the adoption of forensic accounting practices by anti-corruption agencies such as the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC). This study examines the effect of forensic accounting practices (fraud investigation, litigation support, and expert witness testimony) on fraud detection in the Nigerian public sector, using EFCC as a case study. The primary objective was to assess the extent to which these forensic services influence the detection of fraud. A quantitative research design was adopted, utilizing a structured questionnaire administered to 241 EFCC staff across four key departments. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, Pearson correlation, and multiple regression analysis. The findings revealed that while fraud investigation had a positive but statistically insignificant effect on fraud detection, litigation support and expert witness testimony had significant and positive impacts, with expert witness testimony exhibiting the strongest influence. The study concludes that forensic accounting practices play a critical role in enhancing fraud detection outcomes. It recommends that EFCC invest more in training forensic experts, institutionalize litigation support systems, and integrate expert witnesses into its prosecution processes to improve the quality of evidence and ensure successful fraud convictions.

Keywords: Fraud Investigation, Litigation Support, Expert Witness Testimony and Fraud Detection.

Citation: Deshi, N. N., Dang, D. Y., Kujore, O. L., & Lugman, M. (2025). Effect of forensic accounting practices on fraud detection: A study of Economic and Financial Crimes Commission in Nigeria. *SSR Journal of Economics, Business and Management (SSRJEEM)*, 2(2), 79-90.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Fraud is a type of irregularity that involves the manipulation of financial information as well as the misappropriation of assets. The detection is a set of procedures and policies that are applied systematically in order to identify fraud in an organization (Kaunda, 2021). Intuition, suspicion of investigators or managers or an anomaly in accounting records are frequently used to detect fraud (Alhassan, 2021). Financial fraud detection necessitates the addition of forensic accounting to the tools required for successful investigation and prosecution of perpetrators (Anthony & Gavine, 2022).

From the global view, according to KPMG Forensics' February 2022 fraud barometer report in the United Kingdom (UK), the number of alleged fraud cases heard in UK courts in 2021 increased by 66% over the previous year, that is, 298 alleged fraud cases were heard in 2021, up from 180 in 2020 (KPMG, 2022). However, the opposite

trend was observed in terms of fraud value: with the application of forensic techniques, the total value of fraud reaching UK courts in 2021 fell significantly from £724m in 2020 to £444.7m in 2021 (KPMG, 2022). Several accounting scandals in Africa have rendered many public and private organizations bankrupt. For example, the Reserve Bank of Zimbabwe went bankrupt due to accounting scandals (Jephitha, 2020). Corruption has been identified as a major contributor to losses in government institutions in the Western Cape Provincial Government in South Africa (Edheku & Akpoveta, 2020). In Kenya, some practical examples include the near-collapse of the National Bank of Kenya and the collapse of Computer Management Corporation (CMC) motors, which eventually resulted in its sale to Alfatium (Kipng'eno, & Ngahu, 2022).

Several alarming and scandalous cases of fraud have occurred in Nigeria in the last ten years, including the 195 billion Maina pension scam, the \$6 billion fuel subsidy, and the \$20 billion missing from the NNPC and CBN accounts

(Agbata et al, 2022). Fraudulent acts often go undetected, and even when they are, there is insufficient evidence to bring the perpetrators to justice, necessitating the use of forensic accounting (Carroll, 2015). Employing a full-time forensic accountant is deemed too expensive by top management of public entities. Instead, organizations decide to strengthen organizational control structures in order to avoid contracting the techniques of forensic accountants; however, this does not cure the loss of public coffers because, in the absence of forensic investigation, litigation support and expert witness, it would remain a dream and a vocabulary in the public domain (Akelola, 2012; Enofe, et al, 2013; and Jephitha, 2020). Furthermore, Agbata et al, (2022) stated that most high-ranking individuals frequently go unpunished due to a lack of forensic accounting expertise required in prosecuting offenders with the help of solid evidence.

The aforementioned, Bawa (2023) stated that the EFCC lost fraud cases in court due to technicalities. He also stated that the EFCC has been left perplexed by certain judicial decisions in which defendants who clearly stole the commonwealth of the nation and those who aided them were allowed to return home to enjoy their proceeds of crime (punchng.com, 2023). This issue could be the result of a failure to collect proper evidence from the fraud investigation or a faulty presentation of litigation support documents. The issue could also be due to a lack of well-trained expert witnesses to present expert testimony in court. The Nigerian judicial system may require the assistance of an expert consultant to interpret certain forensic technicalities in fraud cases. This necessitates a study on the effect of EFCC fraud investigation, litigation support and expert witness on fraud detection in the Nigerian public sector.

Empirically, most of the previous works were on private sector. This is evidenced by few studies from the Nigerian banking sector, studies such as Okoye, et al, (2020); Eko, Adebisi & Moses, (2020); Tapang & Ihendinihu, (2020); Owolabi, et al, (2021); Edward, (2021); Bello, et al, (2022), while other studies like Mudimba, (2021); Kaunda, (2021) and Kipng'eno & Ngahu, (2022) were conducted in the banking sector outside Nigeria. Other studies were conducted in the manufacturing firms within Nigeria, (such studies as Lawal, et al, 2020; Nandini & Ajay, 2021; Abu, Olatunji & Mike, 2022; Fabian et al, 2022). This study sought to examine the effect of forensic accounting practices on fraud detection by EFCC in Nigeria.

The main objective of this study is to examine the effect of Forensic accounting practices provided by EFCC on Fraud Detection in the Nigerian public sector. The specific objectives of this study are to:

- i. evaluate the extent to which the EFCC's fraud investigation influences fraud detection in the Nigerian public sector;
- ii. analyze the effect of the EFCC's litigation support in detecting fraud in the Nigerian public sector; and
- iii. assess the effect of the EFCC's expert witness in

detecting fraud in the Nigerian public sector.

2.0 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Conceptual Review

This chapter reviewed the key concepts related to the study; Concept of fraud, Fraud Detection, Forensic Accounting, Fraud Investigation, Litigation Support, Expert Witness and Expert consultancy.

2.1.1 Fraud Detection

Detection is defined as actions and activities undertaken to identify and locate prior fraud, both during and after the completion of fraudulent activities. To detect is to discover or reveal the existence of a hidden or obscured fact. Fraud detection should be integrated into an organization's overall anti-fraud strategy, which should include prevention, detection, and investigation (Adegbite, 2021). The detection of actual or potential fraud in an organization is referred to as fraud detection. It is dependent on the implementation of appropriate systems and processes to detect early signs of fraud. Fraud detection entails both proactive risk assessment and reactive response to fraud reports. It also includes enhanced automated data mining and manual spot auditing. Given that it is difficult to observe actual fraudulent activity, fraud usually manifests itself through symptoms. The symptoms may not indicate that fraud has occurred because they are the result of human error. Fraudsters may conceal fraud in human-made errors, making it difficult for forensic accountants to detect them.

2.1.2 Fraud Investigation

Fraud investigation is the act or process of investigating or being investigated, as well as the search for facts; detailed or careful examination. Interview and interrogation are two major investigative techniques used to elicit responses from the suspect or accused. The fraud investigation process starts with a prediction, which is the circumstance that would lead a reasonable, professionally trained expert to believe that fraud is taking place. When there are such indications of fraud, the investigator develops a hypothesis and searches for evidence to support it. Documents, interviews, observations, and other physical clues such as fingerprints can all provide such evidence. The initial hypothesis can be proven or revised based on the evidence gathered (Oyedokun, 2017).

2.1.3 Litigation Support

Litigation Support provides accounting assistance in a matter involving ongoing or pending litigation. It primarily addresses issues concerning the quantification of economic damages. Calculating the economic loss caused by a breach of contract is a typical litigation support assignment. According to Les Nunn et al. (2006), litigation support consulting is a service in which forensic accountants provide an opinion based on known facts or facts yet to be discovered. When the facts are unknown, forensic accountants conduct an investigation and then form an opinion based on their findings. Engagements involving professional liability claims and civil claims are examples

of litigation support services. Quantifying the loss from events such as insurance disputes, delayed construction, and stolen trade secrets is part of professional liability claims consulting. Examples of civil claims consulting include business valuations, employee theft, and accident investigations (Les Nunn et al., 2006).

2.1.4 Expert Witnessing

The concept of expert witnessing can be traced back to the English Courts' admissibility rules in the late 16th century. According to Okoye and Ndubuisi (2020), the first recorded case of forensic accountants serving as expert witnesses occurred in *Meyer vs Selfon* (1817). Since then, the use of core professionals as expert witnesses has gained traction in the developed world. The primary responsibility of such professionals is to assist the court in reaching a decision on issues on which the court may lack the necessary understanding (Okoye & Ndubuisi 2020). Forensic accountants may be called as expert witnesses in accounting-related litigation. Forensic accountants may be asked to prepare a tax analysis, gather economic data, suggest interrogation questions, or assist in the interpretation of documentation. According to (Les Nunn, et al., 2006), the accountants may or may not be required to testify as expert witnesses in court. Serving as an expert witness is both important and difficult. Accounting jargon may be unfamiliar to the judge and jury, so forensic accountants must keep this in mind.

2.2 Empirical Studies Review

2.2.1 Fraud Investigation and Fraud Detection

Abu et al., (2022) investigated the use of forensic fraud investigation on financial crimes detection. The results of the studies showed that there is little connection between the detection of financial crimes and the investigation of fraud. In Nigerian manufacturing firms that are publicly traded, fraud investigation was found to be insignificant for the detection of financial crime. As a result, the study made several recommendations, including that management in Nigerian manufacturing firms hire more forensic accountants who are qualified to conduct forensic financial crime investigations due to their knowledge, expertise, skills, competence, and other factors. This will significantly improve the maintenance, reduction, and detection of financial crimes by Nigerian manufacturing companies that are quoted. The study only looked at the Nigerian manufacturing sectors that were mentioned, leaving room for additional research into other industries. The current study aims to examine the public sector because of this.

Similarly, Lawal et al. (2020) investigated the effect of fraud investigation on fraud detection in Nigeria's manufacturing industry. PZ Nigeria Limited conducted the study, which is considered to be limited in scope. Okoye and Ndah (2019) also investigate the impact of fraud investigation on fraud detection in Nigerian manufacturing industries. Both studies used a survey design, with primary data collected through a structured questionnaire. The studies discovered that fraud investigation has a significant impact on fraud detection in the manufacturing industries. As a result of the studies, the manufacturing industry was

advised to implement a continuous improvement program in the internal control system and to ensure effective and efficient internal checks. In addition, the company should select a reliable accounting system with effective forensic accounting practices. Finally, it is recommended that manufacturing companies hire qualified forensic accountants who are well-versed in the use of appropriate fraud deterrence methods to prevent fraud before it occurs.

Kaunda (2021) in Kenya also conducted an evaluation of the impact of fraud investigation on fraud mitigation among commercial banks. This research was not done inside Nigerian territory. To establish the effect of forensic accounting practices on fraud mitigation, the study used a descriptive survey research design. 41 commercial banks were the intended audience for this study. Since the study aims to gather quantitative data, structured questionnaires were used for the purpose of data collection. Multiple regression analysis, descriptive statistics, and correlation analysis were all used to analyze the data. The study determined that fraud investigation and fraud mitigation in Kenyan commercial banks have a significant and favorable relationship. According to the study, it is important to take preventative measures that can spot warning signs, such as analyzing unusual activity and regularly building up one's capacity. Commercial banks must go beyond simply investigating fraud to include expedited fact-presentation in court proceedings and the use of extrajudicial mechanisms for resolving disputes because doing so improves the chances of recovering the money that was lost.

Additionally, Obafemi (2021) conducted a study in the Nigerian public sector to look at the impact of fraud investigation on financial fraud management. A well-structured questionnaire was given to 250 respondents from the EFFC, ICPC, the Office of the Accountant General, the Office of the Auditor General, and other active accountants in the nation to collect the study's primary data, which was then used in the analysis. Descriptive statistics and regression analysis were used to analyze the data obtained from the questionnaire. The results showed a correlation between forensic accounting investigations and fraud management that is favorable. According to the study, forensic accounting has a significant impact on fraud detection and prevention. However, the scope of the study was limited to select agencies. The study recommends that forensic accounting courses should be included in Nigerian university curricula for the training of accountants from undergraduate to doctor of philosophy levels, and those professional accountants in the public sector be trained as forensic investigators.

According to Ugbede et al. (2021), the fraud investigative approach of forensic accounting has a significant effect on fraud detection in Nigerian deposit money banks. The study suggests that forensic accounting mechanisms and the use of forensic accountant services, which have been identified as the most effective methods, is to be promoted at all levels of money deposit bank activity. In addition, Ugwu (2021) assesses the use of fraud investigation in fraud detection in the Nigerian court process. According to the study, fraud investigation contributes significantly to fraud control. Both studies recommend, among other things, that fraud detection be enshrined as part of auditors'

work by policymakers, so that failure to detect fraud would result in sanctions for the auditor in question. In addition, forensic accountants must be trained and retrained on court procedures in order to avoid losing good cases due to avoidable court technicalities.

Furthermore, Madu-Chimau et al. (2020), Tapang and Ihendinihu (2020), and Okoye et al. (2020) investigated the relationship between fraud investigation and fraud detection in Nigerian banks. A survey of professional auditors and accountants from Nigerian deposit money banks was conducted. The study used a cross-sectional survey research design, with data collected via questionnaires distributed across the banks and analyzed using the ordinary least squares technique. The findings indicated that there is a link between forensic accounting fraud investigation and fraud detection in Nigerian banks. This implies that forensic accounting fraud investigation is an antidote to detecting fraud in the Nigerian banking sector. As a result, the findings strongly support the use and application of forensic accounting investigations in detecting financial fraud in Nigeria. The study recommends that bank management use forensic auditing by amending existing laws so that forensic auditors are integrated into the audit team or committee.

2.2.2 Litigation Support and Fraud Detection

Litigation support was discovered to be statistically significant for fraud mitigation in Kenyan commercial banks (Kaunda, 2021). Similarly, Kirui and Sporta (2020) asserted that litigation support in Kenyan manufacturing firms is statistically significant. Both studies were conducted to investigate the impact of litigation support on fraud mitigation in Kenya. To determine the impact of forensic accounting practices on fraud mitigation, both studies used a descriptive survey research design. Because the study sought quantitative data, structured questionnaires were used in data collection. The data analysis revealed a positive and significant relationship between litigation support and fraud mitigation. It was also determined that the companies used forensic services to help them consolidate evidence and translate complex financial information in order to win fraud cases. Furthermore, it was implied that the litigation support professionals serving as expert witnesses in court had assisted with fraud mitigation. According to the studies, proactive measures that identify red flags, such as the analysis of unusual activities, and capacity building, are required. The need for firms to go beyond investigating fraud and include process expedition in terms of fact presentation in litigation processes, as well as the use of alternative dispute resolution mechanisms outside of courts, because this improves the recovery of lost funds. It was also suggested that Kenyan firms should consider investing in litigation services because they have a significant impact on fraud mitigation.

A study by Bassey (2019) examines the role of forensic accounting in reducing financial crimes (fraud) in microfinance institutions, with a focus on the microfinance banks in Calabar and Cross River State. Therefore, the challenge of this study is to use forensic accounting services to effectively prevent and manage fraud in

microfinance banks. The study used a survey research design. The ordinary least squares method was used to analyze data that were gathered from both primary and secondary sources. Based on the empirical analysis, the regression results revealed that the estimated coefficients of the regression parameter were all negative. The study also revealed that the individual tests of the independent variables were significant; indicating that fraud in Nigerian microfinance banks is significantly reduced as a result of forensic accounting litigation support. Based on the study's findings and recommendations, it is suggested that financial laws be updated to reflect the most recent technological developments in order to guarantee the admissibility of evidence in a court for the successful prosecution of criminal cases.

In addition, litigation support in Nigeria has a significant impact on bank fraud, according to Tapang and Ihendinihu (2020), who looked at the impact of litigation support on unethical behavior in the Nigerian banking sector. Similarly, Ugbede et al. (2021) investigated how litigation functions as a tool for money deposit bank fraud prevention. The study's conclusions also showed that fraud detection in Nigerian deposit money banks is greatly impacted by litigation support. Data for both studies were gathered through the distribution of questionnaires among the banks, using a cross-sectional survey research design. Based on the results of both studies, it can be said that forensic litigation is effective at spotting mistakes and fraud in Nigerian deposit money banks. According to the study, unethical practices in the banking sector should be monitored, detected, and prevented with forensic litigation support in order to maintain effective operations.

The findings of manufacturing companies revealed a positive and statistically significant relationship between fraud litigation practices and fraud prevention. This was the conclusion of Lawal et al. (2020) and Okoye et al. (2019), who investigated the relationship between forensic accounting practices and fraud prevention in Nigerian manufacturing companies. Data was gathered from primary sources by distributing structured questionnaires to the accounting staff of those manufacturing companies. Based on the findings, it was concluded that fraud litigation practices by forensic accountants are an important factor in fraud prevention. Based on the foregoing, it is suggested that Nigerian manufacturing firms improve their forensic accounting practices in order to deter fraud.

Forensic litigation support, on the other hand, was found to have no significant effect on fraud detection in the Nigerian public sector. Obafemi (2021) conducted the research to assess the positive impact of forensic litigation on the recovery of funds lost due to fraud. The study collected primary data through a well-structured questionnaire distributed to 250 respondents from the EFFC, ICPC, the Office of the Accountant General, the Office of the Auditor General, and other practicing accountants in the country. The scope of the study was limited to select agencies. However, the data of the study was analyzed using descriptive statistics and regression analysis. The study suggests that professional accounting bodies in Nigeria increase the number of forensic accountants certified if they have the capacity.

2.2.3 Expert Witness and Fraud Detection

When examined by Dada and Audu (2021), expert witness testimony was discovered to be statistically significant as a tool to prevent tax fraud in federally collected taxes in Nigeria. The study used a survey research design strategy. A structured questionnaire that was given to employees of the Federal Inland Revenue Service (FIRS) and the four major professional accounting firms well-known for providing forensic accounting investigation services in Nigeria was used to collect data. The study found that expert testimony had a significant positive effect on tax fraud prevention. The study recommended that the FIRS staff's training routine be strengthened in order to increase their proficiency in forensic accounting, and that the government considers setting up witness protection schemes to boost expert witnesses' confidence and ensure their safety.

In Kenya, Kirui and Sporta (2020) investigated the effects of expert witnesses on fraud mitigation in firms listed on the Nairobi Securities Exchange (NSE). Although the research was not conducted in Nigeria, it created a gap for a study of this nature to be conducted in Nigeria. Nonetheless, the sample frame was chosen using a non-probability sampling (purposive sampling) technique in this study. Primary data was gathered from carefully chosen employees of the aforementioned firms. The study discovered that expert testimony has a significant impact on fraud mitigation. It was concluded that expert testimony had helped to reduce the possibility of criminal behavior. It was also determined that the companies used forensic services to help them consolidate evidence and translate complex financial information in order to win fraud cases. Furthermore, it was implied that the litigation support professionals serving as expert witnesses in court had assisted with fraud mitigation. As a result, it is recommended that investments in these services be considered because they have a significant impact on fraud mitigation.

Furthermore, Okoye and Jonathan (2019) investigate the relationship between expert testimony provided by forensic accountants and fraud prevention, detection, and reduction. This study is said to have been conducted in Nigerian deposit money banks, whereas the current study will focus on the effect of expert witnesses on fraud detection in Nigeria based on EFCC experience. In this study, a survey research design was used. The methods used to collect data for this study included questionnaires, personal interviews, and document review. A sample of thirty Nigerian DMB branch managers and operations managers was used. The data was analyzed using Pearson moment correlation, and it was discovered that expert testimony provided by forensic accountants has a significant relationship with fraud prevention, detection, and reduction. The study thus recommended that the forensic accountant's work should not only end with fraud investigation but should also and always be invited to provide sworn expert testimony in court that will aid in the prosecution of fraudsters.

Furthermore, expert testimony was discovered to have a significant impact on financial fraud in Nigeria's public sector. Enofe and Aigbepue (2017) confirmed this when they investigated the role of an expert witness in detecting

financial fraud in Nigeria's public sector. In this study's survey research design, data was generated from primary sources using a questionnaire that was distributed in order to obtain complete and accurate responses from the respondents. According to the findings of this study, forensic accountants as expert witnesses in court, expert witness experience, and expert witness education all have a positive relationship with the detection of financial fraud. It is therefore suggested that the use of forensic accountants as expert witnesses in the public sector be increased to aid in the detection of financial fraud. The study, however, did not take into account other important services provided by forensic accountants, such as fraud investigation, litigation support, and expert consulting. Through EFCC experience, the current study aims to cover other important services rendered by forensic accountants in Nigeria.

Enofe et al. (2017) investigated the function and impact of forensic accountant expert witness services in the adjudication of fraud cases in a Nigerian court. A study on expert witnesses and the legal system was also conducted by Enofe et al. (2015). A structured questionnaire was administered to a target sample of respondents in order to collect the majority of the data. Interviews with respondents were also conducted in order to record their responses. The study found that the use of forensic accountants as expert witnesses does have an impact on how cases involving fraud and cases related to fraud are decided. According to the study, forensic accountants should serve as consultants, expert witnesses, and special masters in fraud prosecutions. According to the study, experts should also be evaluated based on the type and extent of their prior professional experiences in light of the particulars of the case at hand. As a result, the current study will evaluate how well the EFCC's expert testimony on the method of fraud detection in the Nigerian public sector performed.

2.3 Theoretical Review

2.3.1 Fraud Hexagon Theory

Fraud Hexagon Theory is used as the underlying theory in this study. The Fraud Hexagon Theory, proposed by Georgios L. Vousinas in 2019, incorporates elements from previous models (fraud triangle, fraud diamond, and fraud pentagon) as well as new elements (Kazimean et al, 2018; Dio et al, 2023). The purpose of this study is to investigate the elements in the Fraud Hexagon model that influence the likelihood of fraud in the Nigerian public sector. Understanding the causes of fraud and using forensic accounting services to detect fraud can help uncover the likelihood of fraudulence activities (Achmad et al., 2022; Dio et al., 2023). It was derived from the SCORE Fraud Pentagon Theory. The acronym SCORE stood for Stimulus (pressure), Capacity (ability), Opportunity, Rationalization, and Ego. However, Georgios L. Vousinas updated and refined the theory by including collusion, which eventually became SCCORE. One of the reasons someone commits fraud is due to pressure. The method takes into account lifestyle, financial needs, and other financial and non-financial issues (Georgios, 2019). The motivation that leads to unethical behavior is referred to as perceived pressure or incentive.

Furthermore, competence is defined as a person's ability to exploit the circumstances around him in order to commit fraud. This is the situation in which a person possesses the necessary characteristics, skills, and abilities to commit fraud. Collusion can be summarized as a secret agreement between two or more people in which one party agrees to bring an action against the other for some evil purpose, with the intent of defrauding a third party of his rights. Opportunity can motivate someone to commit fraud. This opportunity arises as a result of inadequate oversight and abuse of power (Achmad, et al., 2022). An ineffective control or governance system creates an opportunity for an individual to commit organizational fraud. Rationalization either encourages someone to commit fraud or can manifest in people under stress, giving the party the impression that fraud is a natural act (Georgios, 2019). This concept implies that before engaging in unethical behavior, the perpetrator must develop some sort of morally acceptable rationalization. Finally, ego is the belief that one is superior to the authority and rights that they possess, and that the company's policies do not apply to their virtues. Ego can also refer to power over people as well as power over situations. In a nutshell, fraud the hexagon theory is a current theory that inquires deeper into the causes of fraud.

3.0 METHODOLOGY

The research design for this study is a quantitative research design. The survey study research method was used in the study. This study's philosophy falls under the purview of quantitative research approaches, which are offshoots of the positivist paradigm. The positivist paradigm values rationality, objectivity, prediction, and control (Efiong, 2013; Wilken, 2016). The population of this study covered 817 staff from EFCC Abuja command under 14 departments; Forensic and crime laboratories; asset forfeiture, recovery, and management; public affairs; account and finance; internal affairs; intelligence; information and communication technology; procurement and staff welfare service; special control unit against money laundering; administration unit, training unit, policy and statistics unit, organizational support and planning unit, and special control unit (EFCC: strategic plans 2021-2025). The study sampled 4 departments as shown in table 1. The four (4) departments were chosen because they offer forensic accounting services as their key function. This study used stratified sampling technique

Table 1: Population Distribution of the Study

S/No.	Departments	Respondents
1.	Forensic and crime laboratory	63
2.	Assets forfeiture, recovery and management	61
3.	Intelligence	73
4.	Special control against money laundering	67
	Total	264

Source: EFCC Abuja, 2025

The research employed primary data obtained through well-structured questionnaire, which was divided into two sections with a Likert scale of 1 to 5. This is because the study covered parameters that are impossible to directly observe, such as the respondents' perspectives, feelings, and understanding, therefore, the study scale the responses of the respondents in order to derived quantitative data. For data collection, the study used

Google forms to create online questionnaires.

The dependability and internal consistency of the items in the data collection instrument are measured by the reliability of the research instrument. Cronbach's Alpha statistical test was used in this study because it is the most widely used internal consistency reliability estimate. Below are the Cronbach's Alpha statistical test results.

Table 2: Cronbach's Alpha statistical test results

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha	No. of items	Comment
Fraud Investigation	0.706	5	Reliable
Litigation Support	0.781	5	Reliable
Expert Witness	0.821	5	Reliable
Fraud Detection	0.714	7	Reliable

Source: SPSS Version 27 Output, 2025

The Cronbach's Alpha statistical test results for Fraud Investigation Service, Litigation Support Service, Expert Witness Service and Fraud Detection are 0.706, 0.781, 0.821, and 0.714, respectively, according to Table 2. It is clear that all of the variables had Cronbach's Alpha estimates greater than 0.70, implying that the variables in the study were reliable. As a result, the items of the research instrument used to collect data were all reliable for the purposes of this study.

This study used descriptive statistics, correlation, and multiple regression analysis to analyze its data. Descriptive statistics was used concurrently to measure the level of dispersion among all variables, while correlational analysis was used to demonstrate the relationship between the variables. The co-efficient influence of each predictor on the model was examined with the use of multiple linear regression analysis.

3.1 Model Specification

The functional relationship between the dependent and independent variables in the model is presented thus:

$$FDT = f(FINV + LSPT + EWTS) \dots\dots\dots (i)$$

Therefore;

$$FDT = \alpha + \beta_1FINV + \beta_2LSPT + \beta_3EWTS + \mu \dots (ii)$$

Where: FINV = Fraud Investigation LSPT = Litigation Support EWTS = Expert Witness and FDT = Fraud Detection, f = functional dependency of the relationship, α = is the intercept or constant, β_1 , β_2 , and β_3 = are the Coefficients of the explanatory variables and μ = is the error term.

Table 3: Variables Measurement and Source of the study

Proxies	Code	Measurement	Source
Fraud Detection	FDT	The average of responses for the seven (7) items questionnaire using five points Likert-scale to test the effect of forensic accounting services on fraud detection by EFCC Abuja command.	Bello, et al (2022) and Madu-Chimau, et al (2020).
Fraud Investigation	FINV	The average of responses for the five (5) items questionnaire using five points Likert-scale to test the extent to which fraud investigation service by EFCC affects fraud detection in Nigerian public sector.	Oyedokun, (2019) and Madu-Chimau, et al (2020).
Litigation Support	LSPT	The average of responses for the five (5) items questionnaire using five points Likert-scale to test the effect of litigation support service by EFCC affects fraud detection in Nigerian public sector.	Madu-Chimau, et al (2020).
Expert Witness	EWTS	The average of responses for the five (5) items questionnaire using five points Likert-scale to test the effect of expert witness service by EFCC affects fraud detection in Nigerian public sector.	Laws, (2015) and Madu-Chimau, et al (2020).

Source: Author's Compilation, 2025.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 4: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Dev.
FINV	241	1.60	5.00	4.2714	.49418
LSPT	241	1.80	5.00	3.9129	.68742
EWTS	241	2.20	5.00	4.3394	.58550
FDT	241	2.86	5.00	4.2496	.47876

Source: SPSS Version 27 Output, 2025

The descriptive statistics for Fraud Investigation (FINV) show a mean of 4.27, indicating a strong agreement among respondents that fraud investigation is an effective forensic accounting technique for detecting fraud in Nigeria. The minimum score of 1.60 reveals that a few

respondents had relatively low perceptions of its effectiveness, but these are clearly outliers. The maximum score of 5.00 reflects that many respondents rated this technique at the highest level of effectiveness. The standard deviation of 0.49 indicates a tight clustering of responses around the mean, demonstrating a high level

of agreement. Overall, this suggests that fraud investigation is a widely accepted and positively viewed tool employed by anti-corruption agencies for uncovering financial crimes.

Litigation Support (LSPT) recorded a mean of 3.91, which points to a moderately high level of perceived effectiveness in aiding fraud detection efforts. The minimum score of 1.80 implies that some respondents held a skeptical view about its contribution, possibly due to inconsistencies in how litigation support services are integrated into legal proceedings. On the other hand, the maximum value of 5.00 shows that a significant number of respondents believe it is highly effective. The standard deviation of 0.69, being the highest among all variables, reflects more varied responses and a broader range of experiences or opinions. This variability may stem from differences in institutional capacity, legal frameworks, or the frequency of using litigation support in corruption-related cases.

Expert Witness Testimony (EWTS) had the highest mean score of 4.34, suggesting that it is regarded as the most effective among the forensic accounting practices analyzed. The minimum score of 2.20 indicates that while the overall perception is strongly positive, a few respondents may not have experienced or recognized its full utility. The maximum score of 5.00 confirms that

many view it as extremely effective in supporting fraud detection and prosecution. The standard deviation of 0.59 shows a moderate degree of variation in responses, indicating that while opinions are generally aligned, some differences exist—likely due to variability in legal outcomes or the skill of expert witnesses. This strong endorsement underscores the critical role that professional testimony plays in validating forensic findings before legal authorities.

For Fraud Detection (FDT), which serves as the dependent variable, the mean of 4.25 signifies a general consensus that fraud is being effectively detected, likely as a result of applying forensic accounting practices. The minimum value of 2.86 suggests that nearly all respondents rated fraud detection positively, with no extremely low assessments. The maximum value of 5.00 indicates that a substantial number of respondents consider current fraud detection practices to be operating at peak effectiveness. The standard deviation of 0.48—the lowest among all variables—implies a very strong level of agreement, showing that most respondents have similar, favorable perceptions. These findings affirm the positive impact that forensic accounting methods are having on fraud detection within anti-corruption agencies in Nigeria.

Table 5: Correlations

		FDT	FINV	LSPT	EWTS
Pearson Correlation	FDT	1.000			
	FINV	.386	1.000		
	LSPT	.256	.222	1.000	
	EWTS	.695	.419	.197	1.000

Source: SPSS Version 27 Output, 2025

The Pearson correlation coefficient between Fraud Investigation and Fraud Detection is 0.386, indicating a moderate positive relationship. This suggests that as the application or effectiveness of fraud investigation techniques increases, the level of fraud detection by anti-corruption agencies in Nigeria also tends to improve. While the correlation is not very strong, it is significant enough to imply that fraud investigation plays a relevant role in detecting fraudulent activities. This aligns with the understanding that detailed investigative procedures help uncover financial irregularities that would otherwise remain hidden.

The correlation coefficient between Litigation Support and Fraud Detection is 0.256, indicating a weak but positive relationship. This suggests that while litigation support contributes to fraud detection, its influence is relatively modest compared to other forensic accounting practices. One possible explanation is that litigation

support typically comes into play after fraud has already been detected, during legal proceedings. As such, its role may be more supportive than proactive in terms of direct fraud detection, which may explain the weaker association.

The strongest relationship observed in the analysis is between Expert Witness Testimony and Fraud Detection, with a correlation coefficient of 0.695, indicating a strong positive relationship. This implies that the more expert witness testimony is utilized, the more effective fraud detection becomes within anti-corruption agencies. This strong correlation highlights the critical role that expert forensic accountants play in clarifying complex financial evidence, thereby increasing the chances of successful fraud detection and prosecution. Their ability to translate technical financial findings into credible, persuasive legal arguments appears to significantly enhance investigative outcomes.

Table 6: Model Summary

R	R ²	Adj. R ²	Sig.	Durbin-Watson
.711	.505	.499	.000	1.876

Source: SPSS Version 27 Output, 2025

The model summary reveals that the coefficient of determination (R²) is 0.505, which means that approximately 50.5% of the variation in fraud detection can be explained by the joint effect of the forensic accounting practices considered in the model. The adjusted R² of 0.499 slightly adjusts this value downward to account for the number of predictors in the model, confirming that nearly 49.9% of the variance in fraud detection is reliably explained by the independent

variables. The significance value (Sig. = 0.000) indicates that the model is statistically significant at the 1% level, meaning that the predictors have a meaningful impact on fraud detection. Finally, the Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.876 falls within the acceptable range of 1.5 to 2.5, suggesting that there is no significant autocorrelation in the residuals and that the model's assumptions about independence of errors are met. This confirms the overall suitability and reliability of the model in explaining the effect of forensic accounting practices on fraud detection.

Table 7: ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	27.789	3	9.263	80.642	.000 ^b
	Residual	27.223	237	.115		
	Total	55.011	240			

Source: SPSS Version 27 Output, 2025

The ANOVA table assesses the overall significance of the regression model linking forensic accounting practices to fraud detection. The F-statistic of 80.642 is notably high, indicating that the model explains a significant portion of the variation in fraud detection. The associated p-value

(Sig. = 0.000) confirms that the model is statistically significant at the 1% level. This means that the combination of fraud investigation, litigation support, and expert witness testimony significantly predicts fraud detection by anti-corruption agencies in Nigeria.

Table 8: Collinearity Statistics

	Tolerance	VIF
FINV	.804	1.244
LSPT	.937	1.067
EWTS	.813	1.230
Mean VIF		1.180

Source: SPSS Version 27 Output, 2025

The collinearity statistics assess the extent of multicollinearity among the independent variables; Fraud Investigation (FINV), Litigation Support (LSPT), and Expert Witness Testimony (EWTS). All variables have tolerance values well above 0.1 and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values far below the critical threshold of 10,

with FINV (VIF = 1.244), LSPT (VIF = 1.067), and EWTS (VIF = 1.230). The mean VIF of 1.180 further confirms the absence of multicollinearity. These results indicate that the independent variables are not highly correlated with one another and are each contributing unique explanatory power to the model. Therefore, the regression estimates are stable and reliable.

Table 9: Regression Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.306	.224		5.837	.000
FINV	.094	.049	.097	1.895	.059
LSPT	.076	.033	.109	2.314	.021
EWTS	.518	.041	.633	12.488	.000

Source: SPSS Version 27 Output, 2025

4.3 Test of hypothesis

4.3.1 Fraud Investigation (FINV) and Fraud Detection

The coefficient for Fraud Investigation is 0.094 with a p-value of 0.059. At the 5% level of significance, this p-value exceeds the threshold of 0.05, indicating that the effect is not statistically significant. Therefore, the null hypothesis that fraud investigation has no significant effect on fraud detection cannot be rejected. This implies that, although there is a positive relationship, fraud investigation does not significantly influence fraud detection in the context of the model.

4.3.2 Litigation Support (LSPT) and Fraud Detection

The coefficient for Litigation Support is 0.076, with a p-value of 0.021. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected, and it is concluded that litigation support has a statistically significant positive effect on fraud detection. This indicates that variations in litigation support are associated with significant changes in the level of fraud detection.

4.3.3 Expert Witness Testimony (EWTS) and Fraud Detection

Expert Witness Testimony has a coefficient of 0.518 and a p-value of 0.000. Given that the p-value is well below the 0.05 significance level, the null hypothesis is rejected, confirming that expert witness testimony has a highly significant positive effect on fraud detection. Among all variables, expert witness testimony exhibits the strongest impact on the dependent variable, suggesting its central role in enhancing fraud detection efforts.

4.4 Discussion of Findings

4.4.1 Fraud Investigation and Fraud Detection

The findings of the study revealed that fraud investigation has a positive but statistically insignificant effect on fraud detection by the EFCC ($\beta = 0.094$; $p = 0.059$). This suggests that although fraud investigation is positively viewed, it does not significantly drive fraud detection outcomes in the Nigerian public sector. This result contradicts the findings of Obafemi (2021), Kaunda (2021), and Madu-Chimau et al. (2020), who found a significant relationship between fraud investigation and fraud detection across various public and private institutions. However, the findings align with Abu et al. (2022), who reported a weak relationship between forensic investigations and fraud detection in manufacturing firms. The contradiction could stem from implementation gaps, resource limitations, or procedural lapses within EFCC investigations, which reduce the investigative effectiveness in fraud uncovering. According to the Fraud Hexagon Theory, the competence and opportunity elements explain this finding—if investigators lack the capacity or are constrained by institutional inefficiencies, the detection of fraud is likely to be limited, even when investigations are conducted.

4.4.2 Litigation Support and Fraud Detection

The regression analysis indicated that litigation support has a statistically significant and positive impact

on fraud detection ($\beta = 0.076$; $p = 0.021$). This aligns with the findings of Tapang and Ihendinihu (2020), Basse (2019), and Ugbede et al. (2021), who established the relevance of litigation support in exposing and prosecuting fraud in financial institutions. These studies affirm the role of litigation support in translating forensic evidence into prosecutable legal claims. However, the result contradicts Obafemi (2021), who found no significant effect of litigation support on fraud detection in the Nigerian public sector. This contradiction may stem from the variability in the usage or effectiveness of litigation support across agencies; where EFCC may be leveraging this tool more strategically compared to other government bodies. The Fraud Hexagon Theory supports this outcome under the “collusion” and “opportunity” components, as robust litigation services reduce the opportunity for fraud concealment and address systemic collusion through formal legal accountability mechanisms.

4.4.3 Expert Witness and Fraud Detection

The study found that expert witness testimony has a highly significant and positive effect on fraud detection ($\beta = 0.518$; $p = 0.000$), making it the most influential forensic accounting technique examined. This finding is consistent with those of Enofe and Aigbepue (2017), Dada and Audu (2021), and Kirui and Sporta (2020), who highlighted how the use of expert witnesses significantly boosts fraud detection and conviction rates. It also supports Okoye and Jonathan (2019), who concluded that expert testimony helps forensic accountants explain complex financial transactions clearly in court, aiding judicial understanding and outcomes. The powerful influence of expert witnesses may be attributed to their ability to reduce ambiguity in fraud cases and enhance the credibility of evidence. According to the Fraud Hexagon Theory, expert witnesses influence the “rationalization” and “ego” components—by presenting compelling expert testimony, they dismantle rationalizations fraudsters may offer and expose ego-driven fraudulent actions, thereby strengthening fraud detection and deterrence.

5.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, forensic accounting practices are critical to the effectiveness of fraud detection by the EFCC. Expert witness testimony emerges as the most decisive factor, exerting a powerful and statistically robust influence on fraud detection outcomes. Litigation support also plays a significant and indispensable role in enhancing fraud detection capabilities. While fraud investigation shows a positive trend, its current application is insufficiently impactful. Collectively, these forensic accounting methods account for over half of the variation in fraud detection success, making it clear that without their effective deployment, the EFCC’s ability to detect and prosecute fraud will remain seriously compromised. Therefore, the integration and strengthening of forensic accounting practices within the EFCC’s operations is not optional but an imperative for the agency to fulfil its mandate in combating economic

and financial crimes in Nigeria.

It is recommended that;

- i. The EFCC should invest in expanding and enhancing its pool of forensic accounting experts to serve as qualified expert witnesses in legal proceedings, improving the quality and impact of evidence presented in court.
- ii. The EFCC should improve collaboration between forensic accountants and legal teams by establishing dedicated litigation support units, ensuring seamless integration of forensic findings into prosecution strategies.
- iii. Continuous capacity building through training and adoption of advanced forensic accounting tools should be prioritized to improve the effectiveness of fraud investigation processes within the EFCC.
- iv. The EFCC, in collaboration with regulatory bodies, should formalize policies that mandate the systematic use of forensic accounting practices in all fraud detection and investigation activities, ensuring consistency and standardization across operations.

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